

Strokes at the Maradi Referral Hospital: Clinical Presentation, Treatment and Evolution

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Abstract

Introduction: Strokes, with their increasing frequency in sub-Saharan Africa, are on the verge of becoming an epidemic and constitute a real development problem. The aim of our work was to determine the sociodemographic aspects and risk factors of stroke at the Maradi referral hospital. **Patients and methods:** This was a prospective descriptive study from February 15, 2023 to August 15, 2023. Patients hospitalized in the Cardio-Neurology Department and those attending neurological consultations for stroke were included in the study. **Results:** A total of 106 patients were included, including 72.64% (n=72) ischemic stroke and 27.36% (n=29) haemorrhagic stroke. Men accounted for 56.60% (n=60) of cases; mean patient age was 58.10 years; patients aged 50-60 years made up 27.37% (n=29) of cases. Hemiplegia was the most frequent cause (98.11%) (n=104); language disorders were observed in 88.68% (n=94) of cases; headache 62.26%(n=66); balance disorders 83.96% (n=89) and consciousness disorders were rare in 28.30% (n=30) of cases. Stroke risk factors were dominated by: hypertension in 83.01% (n=88) of cases, dyslipidemia in: (Total = 50.57% (n=45), TG = 31.03% (n=27), HDL = 23.25% (n=20) and LDL = 67.82%(n=59) and overweight/obesity present in 68.87% (n=75) of our patients. Indeed, these risk factors for stroke are now fairly well identified; it is currently possible to influence most of them effectively, within the framework of primary prevention. **Conclusion:** In our countries where the technical platform remains limited, especially in terms of the management of these pathologies, it is more than necessary to strengthen primary prevention.

More Information

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Introduction

Stroke is defined as a focal or sometimes global neurological deficit lasting more than 24 hours, which can lead to death with no other apparent cause than vascular origin [1]. Every year, 15 million people have a stroke: 5 million die and 5 million suffer from permanent disability, which is a burden on the family and community [2]. Stroke is becoming an epidemic and a real development problem in sub-Saharan Africa due to its increasing incidence [1]. According to the president of the NGO Alerte AVC Niger>n 90% of patients hospitalized in neurology have a experience after consultations [3]. Indeed, Sonfo A in his study found 81,84% [4]. According to the data from the Niger health statistics yearbooks for 2019 and 2022, the number of stroke cases per year was 2506 and 4040 respectively. Maradi region ranks second after Niamey, with 258 cases in 2019 and 794 cases in 2022 [5]. In response to this increase in cases, we initiated this study, which has the general objective of identifying risk factors for strokes at the MRH.

Materials and Methods

Scope of the study

MRH was used as a framework for our study.

Study type and duration

This descriptive study was conducted at the MRH from February 15 to August 15, 2023, a period of 6 months.

Study population.

This study included patients who were hospitalized in the cardio-neurology department or seen in a neurological consultation at the MRH for stroke.

Inclusion criteria

The study included patients hospitalized or seen for stroke signs with a brain scanner and results the results screening for etiological factors.

Criteria for non-inclusion

Patients whose brain scan did not show stroke.

Data collection

Data were collected from the interviews of patients and/or their parents; the clinical examination of the patient, and the para-clinical examinations through a pre-established survey form. The variables studied were: socio-demographic variables, clinical variables (BMI, blood pressure (BP), abdominal perimeter, sedentary lifestyle, taking of drugs and sympathomimetic substances, cardiovascular risk level), and paraclinical variables: blood sugar, lipid balance

Data Collection and Processing

Data entry and processing were performed using the software Epi info 7.2.5.0 and Excel 2016. We calculated frequencies, averages with standard deviations, and then assessed risk factors by patient occupation. The results were expressed with an alpha error risk < 5%. Data collection and processing was done with the software Epi info 7.2.5.0 and ExcWe2016. We calculated

frequencies, av, ands with standard deviations, and then assessed risk factors by patient occupation. The reares were expressed with an alpha error risk < 5%.

Ethics and Conduct

Data were collected anonymously with informed consent from patients or beneficiaries, without compensation. Authorization for the study was obtained from the authorities of the Faculty of Health Sciences at Dan Dicko Dankoulodo University of Maradi and the MRH.

Results

In total, we surveyed 106 patients, including 60 men and 46 women, with a sex ratio of 1.03.

Socio-demographic characteristics

The 50-70 age group predominated with 48.12% (n=51) of the sample.

Table 1: Distribution of Patients by Age Group

Age group	Frequency	Percentage (%)
[10 – 20]	3	2,83
[20 – 30]	1	0,94
[30 – 40]	6	5,66
[40 – 50]	18	16,98
[50 – 60]	29	27,37
[60 – 70]	22	20,75
[70 – 80]	12	11,32
[80 – 90]	12	11,32
[90 - 100]	3	2,83
Total	106	100,00

Males constituted 56.60% (n=60) of the study population. Two social categories represented the bulk of the sample: housewives (34.90%) (n = 37) and civil servants (24.53%) (n = 26).

Figure 1: Distribution of Patients According Profession

Modifiable stroke risk factors

Eighty-eight (88) patients were hypertensive (83.01%) and in most cases, hypertension had been evolving for more than 5 years.

Table 2: Distribution of Patients by Time of Hypertension Discovery

Duration of discovery of hypertension (years)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
< 5	35	41.67
[5 -10]	17	20.24
[10 – 15]	18	21.43
[15 - 20]	6	7.14
[20 – 25]	6	7.14
> 25	2	2.38
Total	84	100.00

Note: HTA: Hypertension

Forty two patients were diabetic cases, with a mean blood sugar level of 1.43g/l. Diabetes II represented (90.48%) of the cases.

Figure 2: Distribution of Patients by Type of Diabetes

39 patients were smokers, 36.79%; the number of packs per year was variable in these patients with an average consumption of 15.46 packs/year.

Table 3: Patient Distribution by Year

Number of packages per year	Frequency	Percentage (%)
< 10	8	20.51
[10 - 20]	17	43.59
> 20	14	35.90
Total	39	100.00

Moderate alcohol consumption (2 to 3 glasses per day) was found in 6.60% of patient

A total of 99.99 patients were sedentary, 93.40%.

Table 4: Distribution of Toxic and Sympathomimetic Substances According to Drug Use

Drugs	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Oral contraceptives	31	29.25
Cocaine	9	8.49
Amphetamine	1	0.94
Cannabis	6	5.6

Hypercholesterolemia was present in 67.82%. More than 56% of patients were overweight or moderately obese. The mean measured BMI was 28.0138. A total of 67 patients had an abnormal abdominal perimeter (63.21%). The mean abdominal circumference was 95.6981 ±13.0363 and oral contraceptives accounted for (29.25%) of cases.

Table 5: Distribution of Patients According to Dyslipidemia

Dyslipidemia	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Total	45	50.57
Hypercholesterolemia	27	31.03
Hypo HDL cholesterolemia	20	23.25
Hyper LDL cholesterolemia	59	67.82
Abnormal Atherogenic Index	17	19.77
Abnormal LDL/HDL ratio	16	18.60

Table 6: Patient Distribution According to BMI

IMC	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Thinness	1	0.94
Normal	32	30.19
Overweight	38	35.86
Morbid obesity	4	3.77
Moderate obesity	22	20.75
Severe obesity	9	8.49
Total	106	100.00

Note: IMC: Body mass index

Discussion

Socio-demographic characteristics

The study observed a male predominance with 56.60% against 43.40% of women, or a sex ratio of 1.03. These results are comparable to those of Jean-Paul in Mali [6] who also observed a male predominance (54.7%). They are similar to those of Sonfo B and Al in Mali [4] which had observed a male predominance at 56.72%. This is

because sex plays an important role, as the risk of stroke is 1.25 times higher for men than women. These findings similar to Sonfo B and al in Mali, which observed male male predominance at 56.72%. This is because sex plays an important role, as the risk of stroke is 1.25 times higher in men than win women On the other hand, a predominance of women was reported in several study, with 72.39% in Niger in the study by Hantchi et al [7], 50.9% in Mali in the study by Coulibaly S et al [8]. On the other hand, a predominance of women was reported in several s, with 72.39% in Niger in the study by Hantchi et al [7], 50.9% in Mali in the study by Coulibaly S et al [8]. The average age patients was 58.10 years. Yameogo A [9] in Burkina corroborated after finding with 58 years. Alio Hantchi [7] in Niger and Mamoudou T [10] in Mali also found results comparable to ours with 57 years and 57.5 years respectively. By contrast, Ndoumba A recorded an average age of 63.75 years in Cameroon. Age is a major risk factor and it increases, doubling every decade after age 55 [11, 12, 13]. This may be explained by the fact that atherosclerosis, which is a major cause of stroke, most often affects people aged over 40, who are often hypertensive and diabetic [12].

Young subjects are not as spared from the disease, because the minimum age of our patients was 11 years old, Oubandawaki. R [14] in Niger, also reported a minimum age of 24 years. This justifies the search for risk factors requiring the implementation of appropriate preventive measures.

Modifiable stroke risk factors

Hypertension was identified in 83.01% of cases. These results are consistent with the literature and are similar to those of Youssoufa M [15] in Tunisia, who observed a frequency of 81.8%. Higher results were observed in the study of Mamoudou T [10] in Mali (86.11%).

This is because Hypertension is the most important modifiable risk factor associated with more than 50% of ischemic and hemorrhagic strokes [16]. In addition, the relationship between blood pressure and stroke risk exists from blood pressure values of 115/75 mmHg (systolic / diastolic), and it is loglinear. Indeed, every 20 mm Hg increase in systolic or 10 mm Hg increase in diastolic blood pressure is associated with a doubling the stroke risk, regardless of age [17]. The incidence of diabetes was 39.62%. These observations were similar to those of Youssoufa, who reported a frequency of 44.3% in Tunisia. Thus in the literature diabetes is recognized as an independent risk factor for ischemic stroke.

The study reported 36.79% of patients who smoked. These results are higher than those of NDoumba A [18] in Cameroon (6.9%); Traoré F [19] in Côte d'Ivoire (2.2%). These differences are due to regional variations in tobacco consumption and also to the size of our sample. In this series, the LDL hyperlipidemia was

predominant with 67.82% followed by the total hyperlipidemia 50.57%. These results were higher than those of Alio Hantchi [7] in Niger and Coulibaly S [20] in Mali, who had found 46.27% and 43% respectively in their studies. Youssoufa M [15] in Tunisia, in his study had different observations with a higher frequency (72.4%). This could be explained by a change in the eating behaviour of our population. At the end of this study, 35.86% of patients were overweight, 33.01% were obese (morbid 3.77%, severe 8.49%, moderate 20.75%) and total overweight/obesity of 68.87% of cases. At the end of this study, 35.86% of patients were overweight, 33.01% were obese (morbid 3.77%, severe 8.49%, moderate 20.75%) and total overweight/obesity at 68.87% of cases. These results were higher than those of Yameogo A [9] in Burkina who observed a cumulative 44.2% and those of Alio Hantchi [7] in Niger who also observed 39.55%. This may be due to the socio-cultural habits of some patients (lack of physical and sporting activity, especially among women) and the diet increasingly rich in sugar and lipids. Sedentary lifestyle was the most common risk factor (93.40%). Daouda el al [21] made the same observation (93%). This could be explained by the lack of sports culture in our population, especially in urban areas.

Alcohol consumption was found in 6.60% of patients. The STEP survey estimated alcohol consumption at 28% in Burkina Faso, which is explained by our socio-cultural and religious background. Indeed in our society the consumption of alcohol or drugs is frowned upon in addition to the prohibition by religion. Cannabis use was observed in 5.66%. These results are consistent with global cannabis data. Approximately 209 million people, or 4% of the world's population, used cannabis in 2020. The number of people using cannabis has increased by 23% in the last 10 years. This is because cannabis is the most widely used drug in the world [22]. Oral contraceptives were used in 29.25% of cases. Oubandawaki R [14] in Niger reported 11%. According to the publication of FIGARO health in 2018: pregnancy, menopause, hormones are all risk factors specific to women that increase the risk of stroke. And the risk is greater if we add to these hormones smoking correlated with the estrogen-progestin pill.

Conclusion

Risk factors for stroke are dominated in our region by sedentary lifestyle, Hypertension and overweight/obesity. The prevention management of these FDRs must be developed at all levels.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors do not declare any conflict of interest.

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